

THE USE OF EDUCATIONAL AND FIELD TRAINING GROUNDS IN ENSURING PUBLIC SAFETY

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the issues of the use of training and field polygons in ensuring public safety, on the basis of this, the features are highlighted, as well as proposals for its further development are formulated.*

Keywords: *training and field polygons, ensuring public safety, their features.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ УЧЕБНО-ПОЛЕВЫХ ПОЛИГОНОВ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ ОБЩЕСТВЕННОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ

Аннотация. *В статье анализируются вопросы использования учебно-полевых полигонов в обеспечении общественной безопасности, на основании этого выделяются особенности, а также формулируются предложения по его дальнейшему развитию.*

Ключевые слова: *учебно-полевые полигоны, обеспечение общественной безопасности, их особенности.*

Public safety is one of the most important and responsible areas in the activities of the state. Public safety is one of the most important and responsible areas in the activities of the state. This area of activity is related to ensuring the safety and protection of life, health, rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as ensuring public order and preventing threats to national security.

President of the Republic Of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "... how important is the preservation of the peace and tranquility of our people, such as conflicts in the international arena and in our region, radicalism, extremism and terrorism," the statement makes clear the importance of ensuring the security [].

The public safety system includes various bodies and services, such as internal affairs bodies, fire protection, rescue services, security services, etc. Each of these services has its own characteristics and specifics of work, but they are all united by a common goal - protection and ensuring the safety of the population.

In order to function effectively, the public safety system must have trained and experienced employees who can respond quickly and effectively to security threats. In this context, the use of training and field polygons is a prerequisite for personnel training.

Field polygons are specially equipped areas of the territory where conditions are created as close as possible to real ones for training personnel of the security system. At the training and field training grounds, employees can gain practical skills and work experience in various conditions, as well as learn how to work effectively in a team [2].

The use of training and field polygons allows employees of the security system to learn how to make the right decisions in conditions of stress and danger, effectively coordinate their actions and work in a team. In addition, training at field training grounds allows employees to gain the necessary experience working with various types of weapons and other tools that may be necessary to ensure security.

It is important to note that the use of training and field polygons is not only necessary, but also a cost-effective solution. Despite numerous security measures, there are a number of factors

that require an increase in the level of training in this area. In particular, this is due to the need to solve complex tasks that require certain knowledge and skills, as well as the constantly changing security situation. The system of ensuring public safety is one of the most important areas of activity of any state. For its effective work, it is necessary not only highly qualified personnel, but also appropriate material and technical means. However, along with this, experience and the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice also plays an important role. For effective training of personnel in the public safety system, it is necessary to use field polygons.

In this regard, there is a need to use field training grounds in training personnel for the public safety system [2].

Field polygons are specialized facilities designed for practical training and training of employees of the public safety system. They allow you to effectively apply theoretical knowledge in practice and evaluate the results of actions.

A field training ground is a specialized educational institution designed to train and train personnel in the field of security. The use of training and field polygons has a number of advantages over traditional teaching methods, such as lectures and seminars.

The use of training and field polygons has a number of advantages. Firstly, it is an opportunity to conduct training in conditions as close to real as possible. Such conditions are created thanks to specially designed training situations that allow participants to evaluate their knowledge and skills in action.

Secondly, the use of training and field polygons allows you to reduce the training time and improve its quality. Practical training at the training ground helps employees to assimilate information faster and better, because they see its application in practice. In addition, the field training ground allows you to conduct classes in various weather conditions, which makes the training more comprehensive and complete.

Thirdly, the use of training and field polygons increases the safety of training. Specially created conditions at the training ground allow training participants to feel more secure and confident, which is important so that they can focus on the learning process and not be afraid for their lives [3].

Firstly, the training ground allows trainees to acquire practical skills that are necessary in the work of employees of the security system. Various training scenarios are conducted at the training ground, which allow security personnel to put their knowledge and skills into practice.

Secondly, the use of a field polygon allows you to create conditions as close to reality as possible for training personnel. Various security-related situations that may arise in real life can be recreated at the landfill. Also, exercises can be held at the training ground, which allow you to check the effectiveness of the actions of security personnel in extreme conditions.

Thirdly, the use of a field training ground allows for training using modern equipment and technologies. Various simulators can be installed at the landfill, which allow security personnel to learn how to work with modern equipment in practice.

Working in a security system requires certain practical skills and abilities that cannot be acquired only by listening to lectures or watching video tutorials. Security personnel should be able to work in extreme conditions, quickly

The field training ground provides an opportunity for security system employees to apply their knowledge and skills in practice. Training scenarios are conducted at the training ground,

which are as close as possible to real security situations. Employees of the security system can learn how to work in a team, correctly distribute tasks and coordinate actions in extreme conditions [4].

In addition, training on working in extreme conditions is conducted at the field training ground. For example, employees can train in the evacuation of people from buildings in case of fire, act in emergency situations, etc. Such trainings help security personnel learn how to respond quickly and effectively to various threats, as well as make the right decisions in high-risk conditions.

In general, the use of field training grounds in the training of personnel for the public safety system is a prerequisite for improving the efficiency of employees. Creating realistic conditions, as close as possible to real situations, allows security personnel to gain the necessary experience and confidence in working in extreme conditions. Training at the field training ground also helps to build team spirit and learn how to effectively coordinate actions in a team, which is especially important in the conditions of professional development of personnel.

The use of field training grounds in the training of personnel for the public safety system is necessary, as it allows you to create conditions as close to reality as possible for training personnel.

In today's world, where security threats can arise at any moment, the training of security personnel should be as close as possible to real conditions. Field polygons allow you to create situations as close to real as possible, including conditions such as poor visibility, noise, stress, dangerous situations, etc.

Trainings at training and field ranges help security personnel learn how to act effectively in various situations, as well as make the right decisions in high-risk conditions. This is especially important for employees who work on the front line of security, such as police, firefighters, rescuers, etc [5].

An important part of training at the field training ground is the practice of teamwork. Security personnel must be prepared to work together to respond effectively to security threats. At the training and field training grounds, employees can learn to coordinate their actions, communicate with each other, as well as make common decisions in conditions of stress and danger [6, 7].

In addition, training at the field training ground allows security personnel to gain the necessary experience with various types of weapons and other tools that may be necessary to ensure security. This can be both shooting and working with technical equipment, such as radio stations, navigation equipment, etc.

In general, the use of training and field polygons is a prerequisite for the training of personnel of the public safety system.

In conclusion, it can be emphasized that the use of training and field polygons is a necessary condition for the training of personnel of the public safety system. Trainings at training and field training grounds allow employees to gain the necessary practical experience and learn how to work in a team in conditions as close to real as possible.

It is important to note that the use of training and field polygons allows employees of the security system to learn how to respond effectively to security threats and make the right decisions in conditions of stress and danger. In addition, training at field training grounds allows employees to gain the necessary experience working with various types of weapons and other tools that may be necessary to ensure security.

The use of training and field polygons is also a cost-effective solution, since it allows you to reduce training costs and ensure high efficiency of the public safety system.

Thus, the use of training and field polygons is a prerequisite for the training of personnel of the public safety system and allows employees of the security system to gain the necessary practical experience in working conditions as close as possible to real ones.

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